

Chlamydia: A clearer result is needed

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An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

The prevalence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) is on the rise in the UK, with chlamydia being the most frequently reported. Despite its high transmissibility and ease of treatment, many cases go undiagnosed due to a lack of symptoms, leading to severe health complications such as pelvic inflammatory disease, ectopic pregnancies, and infertility. In 2012 alone, 206,912 individuals in England tested positive for chlamydia, with 64% of these cases occurring in those under 25 years old. The increasing infection rate among younger populations highlights a significant public health concern. This research focuses on the barriers to chlamydia testing, particularly the stigma and lack of knowledge surrounding the infection, which contribute to the underutilisation of testing services. A review of four qualitative studies reveals recurring themes such as the embarrassment associated with testing, the pervasive stigma, and the inadequacy of current educational efforts. The National Chlamydia Screening Programme (NCSP) aims to address these issues by providing confidential testing services, yet challenges remain. This study underscores the need for a more holistic approach to STI prevention, which includes normalising STI testing, improving public knowledge, and addressing the psychosocial barriers that deter individuals from seeking care. By analysing recent research, this paper aims to identify strategies to increase testing rates and reduce the long-term health impacts of chlamydia, particularly in high-risk groups such as those under 25. The findings suggest that targeted educational campaigns and more accessible testing options could significantly improve public health outcomes related to chlamydia.

Keywords: chlamydia; screening programmes; sexually transmitted infections; stigma; testing services

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are increasing in the UK, and the most commonly transmitted is chlamydia, which can be easily treated (The Well Project, 2014). Early diagnosis and treatment of chlamydia are crucial to prevent severe health problems such as ectopic pregnancies, pelvic inflammatory disease, and infertility (Public Health England, 2013). Figures from 2012 show that 206,912 tested positive in England, with 64% of the respondents being under 25 (NHS Choices, 2013). These results are pretty disturbing; many who test positive don't suffer from symptoms, resulting in late diagnosis. Public Health England (PHE) suggests that chlamydia makes up 47% of all STI diagnoses (Public Health England, 2014). The Family Planning Association (2010) provides supporting evidence showing an increase of 7% in positive results between 2008-2009 in the under 25s.

The National Chlamydia Screening Programme (NCSP) was developed for confidential service testing, treating people under 25. The testing services are provided at the genitourinary medicine clinic (GUM). Services include STI testing, HIV testing, hepatitis B vaccinations and contraception. Chlamydia was selected as the research topic due to the increasing health threat and the increasing case reports. Since 2002, chlamydia has had the highest STI prevalence. Focusing on chlamydia is extremely important within the younger generation, as results highlight a rise in STIs in the under 25s. Westwood and Mullan (2006) suggest that knowledge of STIs is lacking, as 31% of their subjects could not correctly identify Chlamydia as an STI. However, this highlights the potential for change in education, as poor knowledge can increase the risk of severe consequences.

This research project will involve the review of four research studies, which have been published within the last five years, making the results more reliable. Reviewing the studies will allow an understanding of themes related to Chlamydia. A discussion on the themes will be illustrated, emphasised by the research studies as evidence. The findings of this research can potentially inform policy and practice in STI prevention and control, particularly in the development of targeted educational campaigns and the improvement of testing services.

The review of four research studies

All the research studies analysed used qualitative methodology. The objectives of the four research studies were to examine what their subjects thought and felt regarding chlamydia. After reviewing the studies, reoccurring themes were outlined. These were the barriers of testing, stigma, lack of knowledge, defeating the barriers, and NCSP encouragement.

Barriers to testing

From reviewing the four studies, it became noticeable there was a common theme within three: barriers of testing. Each of these had different interpretations of why there are barriers to testing. O'Connell et al. (2013) suggest that attendees may feel embarrassed as personal questions are asked regarding their sexual history. Embarrassment can cause awkwardness for the patient, causing failure to complete the test. This is supported by a psychosocial framework embedded within the culture affecting people regarding the testing of chlamydia. The framework consists of stigma, embarrassment and fear.

Different testing methods are available, such as home kits, general practice (GP) and GUM clinic testing. Attending a GUM clinic or using home kits can be an uncomfortable experience for the individual, so GP settings can be more appealing. GPs play a crucial role in STI testing, as they can provide a more comfortable and less stigmatizing environment for patients. O'Connell et al. (2013) support the need for GPs to provide STI testing; this would reduce embarrassment for the individuals. The probability of them forgetting to use the home kits or return them to surgery is relatively high. O'Connell et al. (2013) also support that chlamydia should be offered as routine consultation for young people in GP surgeries (Horwood et al., 2020; McCulloch et al., 2020; Santos & Relajo-Howell, 2020). The surroundings would be more comfortable, as other patients would not know why the individual has attended the doctors; however, if the person attended a GUM clinic, its likelihood of attending for an STI tests.

Hesitation can jeopardise the individual's health. Three studies seem to show overwhelming embarrassment, affecting the testing rates. Only one of the research studies suggested an alternative testing service: screening at GPs. All three agree that the overall barrier to testing is linked to the testing methods and emotions of the individual.

Stigma

As stated in the previous theme, stigma is another factor affecting attendance at testing. Social stigma is the disapproval of someone's actions, which others believe can define them, creating a "prejudice and negative attitude" (Avert, 2014; Hoelterhoff et al., 2023; Relajo-Howell & Beckstein, 2023). The stigma surrounding STIs is pervasive as people misinterpret who can catch an STI; however, anyone practising unsafe sex is vulnerable. A range of different reasons for the stigma has been shown in the studies. O'Connell et al. (2013) believe people feel targeted when being offered STI tests, as though the GUM clinic or GP is judging them. This concerns them, as people have a presumption that others will believe they are promiscuous if they accept an STI test.

People who attend the clinic feel targeted by their doctor because the screening service has not been normalised. O'Connell et al. (2013) support this theory, as testing needs to be normalised to prevent people from feeling judged. Rather than the NCSP targeting under-25s, it would be beneficial to target everyone, reducing the risks of people feeling targeted (McNulty et al., 2008).

Many find attending GUM clinics can be stigmatising, affecting their sociality, as it risks creating the wrong impression. Duncan and Hart (1999) suggest that screening is affected by fears of partners and others reacting or leaving due to diagnosis.

Stigma affects people's perceived risks of chlamydia. In three of the studies, it was emphasised that people believed promiscuous individuals are likely to catch an STI. The belief that Chlamydia is not as health-threatening is due to a treatment being available. One of the subjects from Newby et al. (2011) believed pregnancy was more of a worry than chlamydia, while another stated it's simply treatable. This shows a lack of concern regarding the infection because it is curable; however, it can leave long-term health issues. There seems to be a lack of understanding of the risks of chlamydia, as the perceived thought is that if the person has had sexual intercourse with a few people, they're unlikely to see themselves at risk. This suggests that only promiscuous people are associated with the threat. O'Connell et al. (2013) and Newby et al. (2011) agree with this theory, as both studies suggest that only less respectable people would contract an STI.

Only O'Connell et al. (2013) have suggested normalising the testing service. The remaining studies focused on why the stigma affects testing. Due to the stigma, many have a presumption that only negative behaviour can result in testing positive and have a lack of worry regarding contracting chlamydia (Wagg et al., 2020).

Defeating the barriers

One of the main themes emphasised in all four research journals was defeating the barrier of chlamydia testing. NCSP struggle with attendance, and to help reduce chlamydia, improvements are required. As previously stated, normalising the screening services would provide a greater turnout. Conquering the stigma would benefit NCSPs, as there will be a greater chance of attendance at screenings. O'Connell et al. (2013) and Anthonisz (2009) suggest using a better location for testing; however, they recommend a different setting. Anthonisz (2009) recommends a primary area where the target age group, such as community centres, are more likely to attend and feel comfortable. O'Connell et al. (2013) believe GP offering testing will normalise and remove the stigma properties attached. GPs lack an incentive to propose testing Ma, R (2006, in Anthonisz 2009). This suggests that an incentive such as funding may be required for this service to become successful.

Newby et al. (2011) both agree that barriers can be defeated with the power of knowledge. Educating people on threats and providing essential information can change opinions. A subject stated, “Chlamydia is sort of the ones to get” (Newby et al., 2011, p. 147), which shows the lack of knowledge of the seriousness of the infection. Instilling fear in the public regarding chlamydia may increase testing rates. NCSP could adapt these methods to reach a wider audience, creating better awareness of chlamydia.

Lack of knowledge

Another prominent theme is the lack of knowledge, expressed in the other themes. The education provided regarding symptoms, consequences, and testing methods needs to be improved. People need to be aware of the symptoms to detect whether they have chlamydia.

Three of the research studies focused on the lack of symptom education. These all suggested that their subjects had little or no knowledge regarding Chlamydia. When asked whether their subjects knew any symptoms, “I don’t know actually (F8)” (Newby et al., 2011, p. 147) was the response. Newby et al. (2011) stated that the subjects were unclear regarding the symptoms.

The umbrella testing myth is one reason for young males’ lack of attendance, as Bradbeer et al. (2006) suggested who launched an investigation in London regarding this myth. The myth involved using a swab similar to a cocktail umbrella inserted into a male’s urethra and opened. Results suggested the myth has deterred many males from not testing. The myth could be related to previous invasive testing techniques, such as the “use of endo urethral swabs” NHS (2007 in Anthonisz, 2009). This was discontinued in 2001. Invasive testing may result in embarrassment. Devonshire et al. (2000) study shows that only 51% of participating males knew about chlamydia, and the majority were unaware of the consequences. Anthonisz (2009) supports this theory of men being oblivious to the consequences. I suggest that NCSP provide further information for men developing critical awareness. Educating men that chlamydia can result in infertility (Eley et al., 2005). These are all examples of the public’s lack of education concerning the NCSP, as these perceptions result in the absence of testing.

NCSP encouragement

All four research studies emphasised the positive impact the NCSP is providing; however, the rate of chlamydia is still increasing yearly by 15% (Public Health England, 2014). The NCSP must ensure attendees return regularly and deliver the importance of testing. The research studies focused on the impact of the NCSP, why there is a decline in chlamydia testing and the advantages of testing. Anthonisz (2009) suggests that to improve public health, NCSP must make a more significant effort to focus on high-risk categories. Anthony (2009) supports the NCSP, as without it, there will be a lack of knowledge regarding chlamydia and its higher prevalence. Newby et al. (2011) welcome the NCSP for preventing serious health concerns.

The NCSP has been established since 2003, and changes are still required. They aim to control chlamydia spreading through knowledge, research, and better techniques. The new non-invasive technique will encourage people to test. This is supported by O’Connell et al. (2013), who believe that providing early detection reduces health risks. After analysing the themes, the importance of the NCSP is emphasised. The themes entwine one another, as some testing barriers relate to people’s perceptions and lack of knowledge. The NCSP encouragement theme expressed the positive impact the NCSP is having on society. However, the other themes suggested there seems to be a vast amount of negativity surrounding chlamydia. Strategies to overcome these barriers are required to increase testing rates and lower prevalence.

Outlined gaps in current research

There were recurring themes in the research studies. These included a lack of knowledge, which emphasised the misunderstanding of chlamydia. After analysing the studies, gaps in knowledge were

discovered. It suggested there was no research into why there is a lack of knowledge or concern among young adults, considering there were 535,255 diagnoses made between 2003–2013 in people aged between 15–24 (Public Health England, 2013). Newby et al. (2011) suggested an observation on a national scale on what young adults think of chlamydia risks. Highlighting the high prevalence group should be focused on, allowing an understanding of missing links for poor attendance ratings.

There is no research into why people are embarrassed about GUM clinics. The psychosocial framework could affect the individual's thoughts about testing. The three factors must be dissolved to encourage people to attend testing services. Similar gaps were discovered from the research into the themes; these need to be answered to develop a further understanding of chlamydia. Additional research is required to establish how to further build awareness in the youth of today regarding STIs, in particular, chlamydia.

CONCLUSION

Chlamydia remains a significant public health challenge, particularly among young people in the UK. The barriers to practical testing, including stigma, embarrassment, and a lack of knowledge, contribute to the continued spread of the infection. The National Chlamydia Screening Programme (NCSP) plays a crucial role in addressing these challenges, but further efforts are needed to normalise testing, improve public education, and make testing more accessible. By addressing these issues, it is possible to reduce the prevalence of chlamydia and mitigate its long-term health consequences, ultimately improving public health outcomes.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

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